

Apprehension of Monism: the Means

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Abstract

In this note, the author considers the best way to apprehend the unitive state.

Suppose we ask the question - can all experiences be thought of as merely different “degrees” of a single experience? The answer should be carefully considered. If the answer is affirmative, it implies that one reality underlies all experience and such an answer is consistent with the view that one consciousness underlies the whole cosmos. However, the truth of the matter is that, as aspirants, we must strive to remove likes and dislikes until we reach a stage where all experiences are felt to be merely degree-variations of one experience. This would be the practical way to monism.